

DETERMINATION OF THE THROUGH-THICKNESS STRENGTH PROPERTIES TO PREDICT THE FAILURE OF THICK-WALLED COMPOSITE LUGS

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Keywords: Strength parameters, 3D stress state, Arcan, FEA, Cohesive zone model

ABSTRACT

The strength parameters in thickness direction are one of the dimensioning parameters for composite load introductions, which are exposed to complex three-dimensional stress states, like e.g. composite lugs. In the present work a modified version of Arcan's test method was chosen to determine the through-thickness tensile strength. As a result of extensive FE studies, a new specimen geometry was developed which guarantees high reproducibility and accuracy of the test results. The specimen is quadrilaterally waisted with two different contours which ensure a homogenous tensile stress state with only slight stress peaks at the free edges as well as a reproducible failure within the smallest cross section of the specimen. A quasi-isotropic NCF carbon-epoxy laminate representative for aircraft applications is analyzed. Prior to the mechanical testing the specimens are investigated for possible manufacturing-induced defects by ultrasonic stimulated thermography. The determined strength is applied to a cohesive zone model and combined with a modelling method which accounts for intralaminar failure by the application of Puck's 3D failure criteria in Abaqus/Standard. DCB tests and tensile tests on curved beams, where failure occurs in the form of delaminations caused by a through-thickness tensile stress field, are performed. By a comparison of the experimental and numerically predicted failure loads, the through-thickness tensile strength is validated.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the latest generation of long-range aircraft, namely Airbus A350 XWB and Boeing 787 Dreamliner, the amount of carbon fiber-reinforced plastics (CFRP) of the overall structure's mass has risen to more than 50%. Challenging fields of application are load introductions, like e.g. composite lugs, where the locally concentrated load is introduced into the composite structure and causes a complex three-dimensional stress state. High load levels, which are characteristic for aircraft structures and limited design space can result in small edge distances and high laminate thicknesses, typically well above 30 mm. Possible applications for this type of load introduction into composite laminates are for example vertical tail attachments, linkages of high lift systems, main landing gear fittings [1] (see Fig. 1) or the main rotor head of a helicopter. The design of these load introductions is mainly based on experience and substantial testing. In order to qualify composite lugs for further applications within aircraft structures, accurate analytical and numerical methods to predict their failure are needed. In contrast to classical applications of composite materials in thin-walled structures, where a plane stress state can be assumed, the out-of-plane components of the stress tensor cannot be neglected and

may even trigger failure in thick laminates due to low strength in thickness direction. Design methods need to take into account this type of failure and therefore through-thickness design allowables are required. Failure under out-of-plane loading conditions in thick laminates usually occurs in the form of delaminations. This is due to manufacturing-related imperfections or micromechanical stress concentrations at crossings of fibers or yarns within the interface of adjacent layers [2]. To characterize the initiation of delaminations by a suitable failure criterion, the through-thickness failure loads under pure tensile, pure shear and mixed-mode loading conditions have to be determined.

Figure 1: Applications of composite lugs in aircraft structures: linkage for high lift applications (a); landing gear fitting (b).

In the past numerous test methods to determine the through-thickness strength parameters have been proposed in technical publications, most of which are only suitable for one particular load case. A good overview of the available test methods was given by Broughton [3] and Olsson [4]. The through-thickness tensile strength can be determined by tensile tests on waisted block specimens, which are usually bonded to metallic load introduction parts like the one developed by Ferguson et al. [5]. Alternative approaches are bending tests on curved or closed ring specimens. For example Laurin et al. [6] and Leveque et al. [7] carried out four-point bending tests on L-angle specimens in relation to ASTM D6451 in combination with digital image correlation to analyze the local stress state at failure. None of the mentioned through-thickness test methods produces test results with acceptable accuracy and reproducibility, which has already been stated by Hartung [8]. Thus, today there are no existing standards for the determination of through-thickness design allowables for fiber-reinforced composites and there is a great need for the development of further test methods and specimens.

A common test procedure to characterize the material behavior within the whole σ_{33} - τ_{13} failure envelope by a single test rig is based on the test method by Arcan et al. [9]. The original flat circular specimen with two asymmetric cut-outs allows testing under plane-stress conditions and can be installed into a universal testing machine at different angles (see Fig. 2a). Modified versions of this test method to characterize the mechanical properties of composite materials under different load angles were already published in references [10-13]. Therefore, butterfly shaped specimens which represent the region of interest (ROI) of the original specimen are clamped to two metallic half discs and mounted to the testing machine. Based on the fixture of el Hajjar [11], in 2007 Hartung et al. [14] and Tessmer et al. [15] developed a more complex test device, where the load is introduced into the specimen by a form fit between the specimen and the insets. In his work, Hartung [14] stated that tensile and shear loads cannot be tested with identical specimens. Therefore, he characterized the through-thickness failure behavior of HTS/RTM6 carbon-epoxy laminates with two different types of specimens. For tensile loading he proposed a bilaterally waisted specimen with a radius of 12 mm (see Fig. 2b) and for shear as well as for combined shear and compressive loading a bilaterally notched specimen with a notch angle of 15° and a notch radius of 1 mm. Under pure tensile through-thickness loading Hartung determined a strength of 36.7 MPa with a standard deviation of 6.2%.

Figure 2: Specimens proposed by Arcan et al. [9] (a) and by Hartung [8] (b). All dimensions in mm.

The aim of the work presented here is to provide a single test procedure that is capable of all possible through-thickness loading conditions. In a first step the present paper focusses on the determination and validation of the through-thickness tensile strength of a carbon/epoxy laminate. Therefore, a modified version of the test method originally presented by Arcan et al. [9] is chosen. Based on detailed FE analyses an optimized specimen geometry is proposed. The Arcan test results are implemented into a cohesive zone model in Abaqus/Standard and validated by DCB tests and unfolding tests on curved beams.

2 MODIFIED ARCAN TEST METHOD

2.1 Test setup

The test device applied in the current study is strongly related to the one applied by Hartung et al. [14]. The load is introduced into the waisted composite specimen (Fig. 3a, pos. 4) by a form fit between the specimen and the insets (pos. 3). The insets are connected with the half disks of the test rig (pos. 5) by a dovetail clamping, which allows high test rates as well as the installation of different specimen geometries by a change of the insets. A defined relative displacement of the two halves of the test rig is ensured by guide bushings (pos. 1) that are applied to the columns of the universal testing machine (pos. 2). If only the through-thickness tensile strength is of interest, a simplified version of this test setup can be applied to reduce the installation effort. Therefore, only the two insets (position 3) with the negative contour of the specimen and a thickness of 60 mm are used. They are mounted to the universal testing machine by the application of M8 threaded rods with a free length of 40 mm (position 6) and clamping plates (position 7) as demonstrated in Fig. 3b. An accurate alignment of the two insets has to be ensured during installation due to the missing lateral guiding.

Figure 3: Complete (a) and simplified (b) version of the modified Arcan test setup.

2.2 Specimen design

Fundamental requirements to qualify the Arcan test method for the determination of through-thickness strength parameters are the robustness of the test method as well as the accuracy and reproducibility of the results. The latter two can be assessed by the standard deviation of the determined strength parameters. The most reproducible test results in technical publications were presented by Gning et al. [13] as well as by Hartung [8] with standard deviations of around 6%. The specimen by Hartung [8] was already designed to produce a homogenous through-thickness tensile stress distribution but no information about the reproducible location of the failure plane in the tests was provided. To produce reliable through-thickness strength values a standard deviation of less than 5% and a guaranteed failure of the specimen in the smallest cross section are desirable. Therefore the authors developed two new specimen geometries for through-thickness tests with the modified Arcan test method based on an extensive FE study. The specimen geometries used by Hartung [8] were taken as reference and the effect of different geometrical parameters was studied. The final specimen designs should avoid premature failure of the specimens apart from the smallest cross section due to stress concentrations close to the load introduction or at free edges. In contrast, the specimens should allow the accurate determination of the strength by a homogenous distribution of the desired through-thickness stress state within the smallest cross section. Due to these requirements two types of specimen with different geometry are needed for testing under pure tensile and pure shear loading. Only the specimen geometry for through-thickness tensile loading is presented here.

The commercial FE code Abaqus/Standard was applied for the FE analyses. The specimens were modelled by 8-noded continuum elements (element type C3D8) with an element size of approximately $1 \times 1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$ within the region of interest. It was decided to analyze specimens with the quasi-isotropic layup $[45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{\text{ns}}$, which is representative for a lot of applications in aircraft structures. In thickness direction every element row represented four layers. The detailed layup was assigned by the *Composite Layup* option while the constitutive behavior was defined by a linear elastic orthotropic material model for each unidirectional layer of HTS/RTM6 with the material properties given in Table 1. The inner contours of the insets were modelled as rigid bodies. Frictionless contact was modelled between specimen and insets. Load and boundary conditions in conformity with the test conditions were applied at control nodes of the rigid bodies. A load of 4000 N was picked which leads to an average through-thickness tensile stress of 40 MPa.

Engineering constant		Identification	Engineering constant		Identification
E_{11}	[GPa]	120.0	G_{23}	[GPa]	2.9
E_{22}	[GPa]	8.6	ν_{12}	–	0.3
E_{33}	[GPa]	8.6	ν_{13}	–	0.3
G_{12}	[GPa]	4.5	ν_{23}	–	0.5
G_{13}	[GPa]	4.5			

Table 1: Elastic material properties of HTS/RTM6.

After a study on the effect of different geometrical parameters like the number and contour of the waisted surfaces (e.g. two or four faces, continuous radius or straight section with transition radius) the quadrilaterally waisted specimen illustrated in Fig. 4 was developed. This design combines the benefits of two different waist contours. The straight vertical section on the two lateral faces generates a homogenous distribution of the through-thickness tensile stress within the smallest cross section but the small transition radii lead to a large stiffness change, which causes local stress peaks at the transition to the 45° slope for load introduction. In contrast to that, the big radius on the front and back faces leads to a moderate stiffness change at the transition area. In addition, it clearly defines the smallest cross section in the center of the specimen where failure should occur. The homogenous σ_{33} -distribution within the smallest cross section of the developed specimen is demonstrated in Fig. 5b.

Compared to the reference specimen by Hartung [8] (see Fig. 5a) it features a more homogenous stress distribution with only low stress peaks at the free edges of 12% of the average through-thickness tensile stress within the smallest cross section ($\bar{\sigma}_3$). In addition to the quasi-isotropic laminate, the stress concentration has also been evaluated for a unidirectional laminate with fibers aligned in x-direction. Since no change of the stress distribution within the smallest cross section was observed if the layup is changed, the developed specimen is also fitted for the testing of unidirectional laminates. In sum, the developed specimen promises a high potential to determine the through-thickness tensile strength of composites with high accuracy and reproducibility.

Figure 4: Geometry of the developed specimen for through-thickness tensile tests. All dimensions in mm.

Figure 5: Through-thickness tensile stress distribution within the smallest cross section of the reference specimen from [8] (a) and the developed specimen (b).

2.3 Specimen manufacturing

In a first step, a plate with a thickness of 36 mm, the quasi-isotropic layup $[45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{ns}$ and a fiber volume fraction of approximately 60% was manufactured. Saertex biaxial NCF (Toho Tenax HTS carbon fibers with polyester stitching yarn) was infiltrated with a Hexcel RTM6 epoxy resin by a vacuum-assisted resin infusion process (VAP) and cured at a temperature of 180 °C. Cuboidal blocks were machined out of the plate by water-jet cutting. The final shape of the specimens was CNC milled with several roughing processes and one finishing process. The machined specimens were investigated for possible micro-cracks introduced by manufacturing. Each specimen was analyzed by ultrasound-induced thermography. The ultrasound stimulation with a frequency of 20 kHz causes relative displacement and friction between the faces of a crack, which result in heat dissipation that can be detected by a thermo camera. With this method subsurface cracks could be detected at some of the specimens (see Fig. 6). As a consequence, these specimens were excluded for the determination of through-thickness strength properties due to the high risk of premature failure apart from the smallest cross section during the mechanical tests.

Figure 6: Results of ultrasound-induced thermography: specimen with (a) and without subsurface crack (b).

2.4 Test results

The through-thickness tensile tests were carried out with the simplified test setup presented in chapter 2.1 on a 10 kN capacity Instron uniaxial universal testing machine at an extension rate of 0.5 mm/min. The test series consisted of six specimens. Three of the tested specimens were instrumented with a strain gauge in the center of the front and back face to enable the determination of the Young's modulus E_{33} . Small strain gauges with a measuring length of only 1 mm were chosen due to the variation of the cross section along the specimen's thickness direction.

As supposed, all specimens failed within the smallest cross section (see Fig. 7). The test results are summed up and compared to the in-plane transverse material properties in Table 2. The Young's modulus E_{33} was calculated between strain values of 0.05% and 0.25%. It has to be treated with caution due to the small gauge length and the varying cross-section of the specimen in thickness direction. The measured E_{33} of the laminate of 8.4 GPa with a standard deviation of 0.4% corresponds to the in-plane transverse modulus of a uni-directional layer of 8.6 GPa. According to 3D lamination theory, $E_{33,QI}$ should be higher than $E_{33,UD}$ caused by constraining of transverse contraction. A through-thickness tensile strength R_3^t of 45.4 MPa was determined with a standard deviation of 4.4%. Compared to the through-thickness tensile strength for the same material presented in [8] (36.7 MPa, $s = 6.2\%$), the determined strength is higher and more reproducible which both can be explained by the more homogenous stress distribution within the smallest cross-section already mentioned in chapter 2.2.

Fig. 7. Failed specimen after test.

Material property		Direction	
		2 (UD)	3 (QI)
R_{ii}^t	\bar{x} [MPa]	67.0	45.4
	s [%]	13.4	4.5
E_{ii}^t	\bar{x} [MPa]	8.6	8.4
	s [%]	1.3	0.4

Table 2: Transverse material properties of HTS/RTM6.

3 VALIDATION

To validate the determined through-thickness tensile strength, DCB and unfolding tests were carried. In both test cases failure is triggered by tensile stresses in thickness direction. The experimentally determined through-thickness tensile strength was implemented into FE models. By progressive failure analysis the failure loads of both test cases were predicted and compared to the test results.

3.1 Modelling method

The modelling method presented in this paper accounts for progressive intralaminar as well as interlaminar failure. Different approaches are chosen for the two types of failure in composite materials and then combined in one FE model in Abaqus/Standard. Based on the modelling method already applied for the Arcan specimen, intralaminar failure is implemented by a user defined material model (UMAT). The UMAT implies Puck's action plane failure criteria [16] in combination with a simplified damage propagation approach, as it was applied by Deuschle [17]. Failure occurs if the stress exposure for fiber failure (f_{E_FF}) or for inter-fiber failure (f_{E_IFF}) is equal to one. Damage initiation is followed by a stiffness degradation of the affected layer to allow for damage propagation in the model. In the case of inter-fiber failure, under increasing load the stress exposure f_{E_IFF} is kept constant at the level of one by a continuous degradation of the matrix-dominated elastic material properties. Total failure of the layer occurs if it suffers fiber failure. As a consequence all moduli are abruptly reduced to a pre-defined minimum value. It has to be stated that this modelling method is only feasible for multi-directional laminates.

To account for interlaminar failure, a cohesive zone model is implemented into the FE model in the form of a contact formulation between sublaminates. A bilinear cohesive law (see Fig. 8) is defined for each of the fracture modes I, II and III by the stiffness K_i ($i = I, II, III$), the traction at crack initiation τ_i^0 and the corresponding critical energy release rate (CERR) G_{iC} . Under mode I loading conditions the Arcan through-thickness tensile strength determined in this work was applied as τ_I^0 . The critical energy release rates G_{IC} and $G_{IIIC} = G_{IIIIC}$ were determined by DCB and ENF tests whereas the remaining strength parameters τ_{II}^0 and τ_{III}^0 were taken from Alfano et al. [18]. An overview of the defined parameters of the cohesive law is given in Table 3. To account for failure under mixed-mode-loading conditions, a quadratic stress criterion is applied for damage initiation and damage evolution is controlled by the Benzeggagh and Kenane criterion [19] with an exponent of 2.274.

Parameter	Mode		
	I	II	III
K_i [N/mm ³]	10^6	10^6	10^6
τ_i^0 [MPa]	45.4	60.0	60.0
G_{iC} [N/m]	384.8	1996.0	1996.0

Figure 8: Definition of cohesive law.

Table 3: Parameters of cohesive law for HTS/RTM6.

3.2 DCB tests

The DCB tests following DIN EN 6033 were performed on beam specimens ($250 \times 25 \times 3.4$ mm³) of HTS/RTM6 with the layup [0/90/45/-45/90/0]_s. The specimens were pre-cracked in the symmetry plane by the insertion of a 0.02 mm thick Teflon layer at one end. Under quasi-static loading conditions a mode I CERR of 384.8 N/m with a standard deviation of 4.3% was determined with a number of 5 specimens. An average load at initiation of crack propagation P_{ini} of 92.5 N with a standard deviation of 3.3% was observed.

Figure 9: DCB test (a) and numerical model (b).

In the numerical model (see Fig. 9b) the specimen was divided into two sublaminates with a cohesive contact formulation defined between the bonded surfaces. The mesh dependency of cohesive zone models in numerical analyses is a well-known fact and has been reported among others by Turon [20]. Therefore a mesh convergence study has been conducted with in-plane mesh sizes between $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ mm}^2$ and $0.25 \times 0.25 \text{ mm}^2$. Convergence of P_{ini} and the load-displacement-curves was observed at an in-plane mesh size of $0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^2$ (see Table 5). The predicted load-displacement-curve of the converged numerical solution is in very good agreement with the experimental results with a slight overestimation of P_{ini} of less than 10% (see Fig. 10).

l_e [mm]	P_{ini} [N]
2.50	346.1
2.00	269.2
1.50	206.9
1.00	146.7
0.50	101.8
0.25	101.6

Table 5: Mesh convergence study. Figure 10: Load-displacement-curves of tests and converged numerical solutions.

3.3 Unfolding tests

For further validation of the determined through-thickness tensile strength the curved beam specimen illustrated in Fig. 11a was chosen. The specimen correlates to the one applied by Roos [21] to validate interlaminar failure modelling and consists of a 90° angle in the center and two 135° angles with different radii. With this geometry the specimen represents typical load bypasses, which are present in lots of applications, e.g. in OMEGA profiles. If the specimen is loaded under tension in x-direction the angles unfold and a through-thickness tensile stress field develops in the 90° angle (see Fig. 11b), which causes failure of the specimen due to delamination. The specimens with the layup $[90/0/-45/45/0/90/45/-45/90/0]_s$ were manufactured of HTS/RTM6 by a vacuum assisted infiltration process with an open male mold.

Figure 11: Specimen geometry (a) and σ_{33} -distribution during unfolding tests (b).

Five specimens were tested under quasi-static loading conditions. During the tests the specimen showed the desired failure behavior. A representative load-displacement curve is given in Fig. 12a. At an average load of 1276.0 N with a standard deviation of 8.5% initial failure occurred in terms of a delamination in the symmetry plane of the 90° angle which caused a sudden load drop. Thereafter the load increased again with a reduced stiffness until further delaminations developed in adjacent interfaces which were characterized by load drops again. The growth of the interlaminar cracks into the legs of the specimens was stable until a certain point where instable crack growth led to an abrupt propagation of the cracks over the whole specimen length. The specimen was able to transmit load until fiber failure occurred at a displacement of more than 15 mm.

Figure: 12. Unfolding tests: Representative load-displacement curve (a) and failure behavior (b).

In the FE model of the unfolding tests the specimen was divided into 4 sublaminates which were connected by cohesive contact formulations. Due to the results of the DCB simulation an in-plane mesh size of $0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^2$ was chosen for the critical area of the unfolding specimen. In thickness direction every sublaminate was discretized by two element rows, resulting in an element thickness of 0.625 mm. With the combined modelling approach for intra- and interlaminar failure the FE model gave a good representation of the experimental results in terms of force-displacement curve and phenomenological failure behavior (see Fig. 13). The first delamination within the symmetry plane at a load of 1300.0 N is followed by intralaminar failure in the adjacent unidirectional layers. As a consequence of the developing stress concentrations intralaminar failure in the surrounding layers and further delaminations in neighboring interfaces are caused. The load level after initial failure is

overpredicted by a certain amount which is caused by the simplified $f_{E_IFF} = 1$ stiffness degradation approach after intralaminar inter-fiber failure.

Figure 13: Numerical analysis of unfolding tests: load-displacement curve (a) and failure behavior (b).

By the simulation of DCB and unfolding tests the through-thickness tensile strength determined by Arcan tests could be validated. In addition, the applied modelling method shows a high potential to account for combined progressive intra- and interlaminar failure. As a consequence, both can be utilized for the failure analysis of complex CFRP load introductions, like e.g. composite lugs.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper a new specimen geometry for the determination of the through-thickness tensile strength of composite laminates with a modified Arcan test setup was developed based on the results of detailed FE analyses. Compared to existing specimen geometries from technical publications, the developed one features a more homogenous stress distribution within the fracture plane. Therefore, its application should induce higher accuracy and reproducibility of the test results. For the quasi-isotropic HTS-carbon/epoxy laminate under investigation a through-thickness tensile strength of 45.4 MPa with a standard deviation of 4.5% and a through-thickness tensile Young's modulus of 8.4 GPa with a standard deviation of 5.8% were determined. The strength parameter was implemented into FE models as threshold for interlaminar failure by the application of a cohesive zone model and validated by DCB and unfolding tests. The failure loads were numerically predicted with a maximum deviation of 10% compared to experimental results. The presented modelling method for combined intra- and interlaminar failure showed a high potential to predict failure under complex loading conditions.

To complete the characterization of the failure behavior within the whole $\sigma_3^t - \tau_{13}$ envelope, Arcan tests under pure shear and combined tensile and shear load will be carried out³ with a newly developed shear specimen geometry. To validate the determined shear strength, ENF and short beam bending tests will be performed in combination with nonlinear FE analyses. Finally, the calibrated modelling method, which is capable of progressive intra- and interlaminar failure under 3D loading conditions, will be applied for the failure analysis of composite lugs and support the generation of design guidelines for this type of load introduction.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The support of the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) in the project MAI Last, as part of the leading-edge cluster MAI Carbon under grant 03MAI13A, is gratefully acknowledged. The authors wish to thank Christian Deimling and Sebastian Holzeder for their contribution during their theses. The authors also thank Kurt Pfeffer for the mechanical testing activities.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Zimmermann, D. Zenkert and M. Siemetzki, Testing and analysis of ultra thick composites. *Compos Part B: Eng*, 41, 2010; pp. 326-336.
- [2] A. Puck, *Festigkeitsanalysen von Faser-Matrix-Laminaten: Modelle für die Praxis*, 1st ed., Hanser, Munich, 1996, p. 151f.
- [3] W. R. Broughton, Through-thickness testing, *Mechanical testing of advanced fibre composites (Ed. J. M. Hodgkinson)*, 1st ed, Woodhead, Cambridge, 2000, pp. 143-169.
- [4] R. Olsson, A survey of test methods for multiaxial and out-of-plane strength of composite laminates, *Compos Sci Technol*, 71, 2011; pp. 773-783.
- [5] R. F. Ferguson, M. J. Hinton and M. J. Hiley, Determining the through-thickness properties of FRP materials, *Compos Sci Technol*, 58, 1998, pp. 1411-1420.
- [6] F. Laurin, J. S. Charrier, D. Leveque et al., Determination of the properties of composite materials thanks to digital image correlation measurements, *Procedia IUTAM*, 4, 2012, pp. 106-115.
- [7] D. Leveque, F. Laurin, A. Mavel et al., Investigations on failure mechanisms of composite structures subjected to 3D state of stresses, *Proceedings of SEM annual conference (Ed. T. Proulx)*, June 2010, Indianapolis, pp. 33-42.
- [8] D. Hartung, *Materialverhalten von Faserverbundwerkstoffen unter dreidimensionalen Belastungen*, PhD thesis, University of Braunschweig, April 2009.
- [9] M. Arcan, Z. Hashin and A. Voloshin, A method to produce uniform plane-stress states with applications to fiber-reinforced materials, *Exp Mech*, 18, 1978, pp. 141-146.
- [10] S. C. Yen, J. N. Craddock and K. T. The, Evaluation of a modified Arcan fixture for the in-plane shear test of materials, *Exp Techniq*, 12, 1988, pp. 22-25.
- [11] R. El-Hajjar and R. Haj-Ali, In-plane shear testing of thick-section pultruded FRP composites using a modified Arcan fixture, *Compos Part B: Eng*, 35, 2004, pp. 421-428.
- [12] D. Delsart and J. M. Mortier, Identification of the interface properties of fibre reinforced composite materials, *Proceedings of SEM XIth International Congress and Exposition on Experimental & Applied Mechanics*, Orlando, June 2008.
- [13] P. B. Gning, D. Delsart, J. M. Mortier et al, Through-thickness strength measurements using Arcan's method, *Compos Part B: Eng*, 41, 2010, pp. 308-316.
- [14] D. Hartung, L. Aschenbrenner and J. Tessmer, Analysis of the through-thickness material and failure behaviour of textile composites. *Proceedings of Composites 2007 - ECCOMAS thematic conference on mechanical response of composites*, Porto, May 2007.
- [15] J. Tessmer, D. Hartung and L. Aschenbrenner, Mechanics of composites in lightweight structures: Efficient testing and computation accounting for complex 3d behaviour, *Proceedings of 26th Congress of international council of the aeronautical sciences*, Anchorage, September 2008.
- [16] M. Knops, *Analysis of failure in fiber polymer laminates: the theory of Alfred Puck*, Springer, Berlin, 2008.
- [17] H. M. Deuschle, *3D Failure analysis of UD fibre reinforced composites: Puck's theory within FEA*, Phd Thesis, ISD, University of Stuttgart, 2010.
- [18] G. Alfano and M. A. Crisfield, Finite element interface models for the delamination analysis of laminated composites: mechanical and computational issues, *Int J Numer Meth Eng*, 50, 2001, pp. 1701-1736.
- [19] M. L. Benzeggagh and M. Kenane, Measurement of mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness of unidirectional glass/epoxy composites with mixed-mode bending apparatus, *Compos Sci Technol*, 56, 1996, pp. 439-449.

- [20] A. Turon, C. G. Davila, P. P. Camanho et al., An engineering solution for mesh size effects in the simulation of delamination using cohesive zone models, *Eng Fract Mech*, 74, 2007, pp. 1665-1682.
- [21] R. Roos, *Model for interlaminar normal stresses in doubly curved laminates*, PhD thesis, ETH Zurich, 2008.